

Artificial Neural Networks AutoEncoders an Overview

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31 July 2022

Abstract

AutoEncoders are the simplest and most powerful type of Artificial Neural Network in Artificial Intelligence that can be applied in multiple domains. AutoEncoders are Artificial Neural Network structures that are used with the purpose of extracting valuable and often hidden features from the original input that they given. AutoEncoders consist of many types but all the types are composed of a basic general structure that comprises of an Encoder , Decoder and an Activation Function for either linear mapping or non-linear mapping to process the input that has been given. In this research paper the different types of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders will discussed along with the different components they are comprised of as well as their operations. The application of some of these types of AutoEncoders shall be discussed within their own domains. This research paper is aimed at giving the reader a basic understanding of the AutoEncoder and to act as basis for future researches in the field of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders.

Keywords: Artificial Neural Network, Auto Encoders, Compression, Artificial intelligence, Computational intelligence, Dimensionality Reduction, Machine Learning , AutoEncoder Recommender Systems , AutoEncoder Classification

Introduction

Artificial Neural Networks are apart of the Artificial Intelligence realm. Artificial Neural Networks attempt to simulate and copy the functioning and operations of the Biological Neurons in Human Beings. Artificial Neural Networks are Artificial Intelligence structures that consists of input layers , hidden/middle layers and an output layer. Input layers typically perceive their inputs from their sensors that read data from their environment of operation. Hidden/Middle layers perform the majority of the computation that occurs inside of the Neural Networks in which with the use of weighted inputs they compute the desired output for the system. Artificial Neural Networks are very popular for solving the most complex nonlinear problems. Some Types of Artificial Neural Networks such as AutoEncoders have the capability of dealing with unlabeled data with ease and are used in domains where the data is usually vague and not classified to specific classifications. Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders have been implemented in a variety of domains due to their capabilities in solving non-linear problems with vague data sets these domains include Recommender Systems for recommending different sorts of products to different sets of users , Classification of data into certain categories based on the features of the data

and Clustering of the data into clusters based on similar features.

This Paper examines the Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoder types and the parts they are composed of and how each one of them operate. The domains of the application of the Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders shall be discussed and how the AutoEncoders operate in those domains.

Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders

Artificial Neural Networks are networks that comprise of multiple layers of neurons that take an input through the agent's sensors while perceiving its own environment of operation and result in an output by using an activation function to process the data using the hidden input layers that use the weighted connections to determine the desired output by the system and to portray it using the most suitable representation [3,6]. The concept of learning in Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is to find the set of weights in the layers that makes the system behave in the desired way and to allow the system to output the desired results [6]. Artificial Neural Networks can be used in solving many complex nonlinear problems [3]. Auto Encoders are the most basic structures of the Artificial Neural Networks that simply takes an input and transforms the input into a compressed representation and decodes the input to come up with an output that is the creation of the original input from the compressed representation of the original input to learn about the most important features of the input in the form of a "dense" representation of the input [1,12]. AutoEncoders are unsupervised training models that use unsupervised learning algorithms that deals with unlabeled sets of data by extracting the most important features of the original input by reconstructing the original input from the hidden/compressed version of the input that is used to train the model to learn[3,6]. The representation of the data then can be used in many other applications and domains such as clustering by extracting meaningful and important features from the proposed data input[1]. The Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoder mainly consists of two main parts which are the encoder and the decoder [2]. The encoder in AutoEncoder

is a mapping function that takes an input vector with d-dimension to generate a hidden representation of the input data[6]. The Decoder is also a mapping function that reconstructs the compressed version of the original input by extracting the most important features from the hidden/compressed version of the original input and generating the output in the form of a vector that is the "dense" representation of the original input that contains all the necessary features along with the extracted features from the original input [2,6,12]. The Similarity/Distance in the original dimension space which is the original input taken by the Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoder is calculated for each point labeled as (xi) to determine the reconstruction set for the output which is reconstructed based on the original input [2]. The encoder takes the input (Xi) and encodes it to its reduced hidden/Compressed representation by using either the identity function for linear mapping in order to output a real value that does not fall in a specific range or the sigmoid function which is expressed as $(\frac{1}{1+e^{-w_x}})$ for non-linear mapping [2,6]. Those two functions are labeled as the g() of the equation when applied, in which the g() takes either the Identity function or the sigmoid function in order to encode the input to its reduced hidden/compressed representation for later reconstruction by the decoder [2]. The W of the equation are the weighted matrix of dimensions that is expressed as (dx * dy) of the equation [2]. The reduced hidden/compression function is labeled as the (Yi) as it is portrayed in (figure 1) as it is originally labeled in [2].

$$y_i = g(Wx_i)$$

Figure 1 : The equation for the encoding process from [2]

The decoder performs the decoding process by reconstructing the hidden/compressed representation of The input labeled as (Yi) by performing the identity function for linear

reconstruction of the input or the sigmoid function for a binary representation or reconstruction of the input data to extract the necessary and the important features from the compressed representation of the original input and attempt to reconstruct the original input from the hidden/compressed input representation [2]. The equation can be expressed as the formula derived from [2] shown in (figure 2)

$$x'_i = f(W' y_i)$$

Figure 2 : The equation of the decoding process from [2]

The $\overline{(X_i)}$ refers to the reconstructed input that has been reconstructed by the use of either the identity function for linear reconstruction or the sigmoid function for binary reconstruction in which either one is labeled as the $f()$ of the equation with the another $\overline{(W)}$ for the $(dx * dy)$ weight matrix to reconstruct the original input from the hidden/compressed representation of the input [2].

1. Sparse AutoEncoder

The Sparse AutoEncoders are a type of AutoEncoders that are symmetrical and used for extracting features from a set of unsupervised data[7]. AutoEncoders commit the process of increasing the scatteredness of the data through Sparsity(Scatteredness) Induction to enforce Sparsity Regularization [1]. The Sparsity AutoEncoder uses a Sparsity constraint on the backpropagation algorithm when dealing with lesser hidden layers than the original input which is leading to a compressed representation of the input data [3]. First the Average Activation of the hidden layer units (j) shall be calculated before

introducing the (Sparsity Parameter) [3] as shown in (figure 3) from [3]

$$\hat{\rho}_j = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left[a_j^{(2)}(x^{(i)}) \right]$$

Figure 3 : The equation of Average Activation of the hidden layer units (j)

Second we assign the (Sparsity Parameter) which is labeled as (ρ) which is a value that normally falls close to the value of (0) to the Activation Function value of each hidden layer neuron to presume or enforce the Sparsity constraint in order for each hidden layer's neuron average activation to be near the (Sparsity Parameter) value (ρ) [3]. The assignment is shown in (figure 4) received from [3].

$$\hat{\rho}_j = \rho,$$

Figure 4 : The Assignment of the Sparsity Parameter to the Average Activation Function Value

For the sake of optimization we shall use the algorithm shown in (figure 5) derived from [3] by creating a penalty term to get a more accurate set of results.

$$\sum_{j=1}^{s_2} \rho \log \frac{\rho}{\hat{\rho}_j} + (1 - \rho) \log \frac{1 - \rho}{1 - \hat{\rho}_j}.$$

Figure 5 : The Penalty Term equation

The (s_2) in the penalty term equation is referring to the number of hidden layer neurons and the index (j) is referring to the sum of all the hidden layer neurons in the model in which the equation is

originally based on the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence formula[3].The Kullback-Leibler (KL) equation is the sparsity constraint enforcement for reducing the reconstruction error that happens from the reconstruction of the original input by the decoder in which it computes two different distributions (features) between the target activation function of the hidden/middle layer neurons labeled as (p) and the j Th hidden/middle layer neuron[7,8].(KL) formula calculates the probability of two distributions to determine to what extent is the first distribution different from the second distribution as it is shown in the following equation which is based on the original equation received from [10] as shown in (figure 6)

$$D_{KL}(p || q) = \sum p(x) \log \left[\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} \right]$$

$$D_{KL}(p || q) = \sum_i p_i \log_2 \frac{p_i}{q_i}$$

Figure 6 : Kullback-Leibler (KL) formula for probability distribution.

The (D_{KL}) is the distribution formula of (q from p) in which both [p] and [q] are discrete probability distributions.The distribution formula of (D_{KL}) is assigned a non-negative value that is (≥ 0) when distribution (q) is calculated along with the true distribution (p) in order to determine if the distributions are matching in which the value of (0) is received if they are both matching [10].(KL) formula calculates the information gained when distribution (q) is used instead of distribution (p) in the process of extracting features from the original input in its hidden/compressed version.

The Sparse AutoEncoder apart from the mentioned equations, has an Encoder that maps the input vector (X_i) to its hidden/compressed representation that is labeled as (h_i) as shown in (figure 7) received from [7].

$$h_i = g(W^{(e)}x_i + b^{(e)})$$

Figure 7 : The Encoding equation for the Sparse Autoencoder

The (W) of the equation refers to the weight matrix of the Encoder [7], that comprises of the multiplication of the (x) and (y) dimensions to form ($dx * dy$).The (b) is the bias value or vector of the encoding equation [7], which is used to regulate or shift the activation function by a constant value.The most preferred activation function for the Sparse AutoEncoder is the Sigmoid function for non-linear mapping [7]. The Sparse AutoEncoder has a Decoding equation that is shown in (figure 8) as received from [7].

$$\hat{x}_i = g(W^{(d)}h_i + b^{(d)})$$

Figure 8 : The Decoding equation for the Sparse Autoencoder

The (\hat{X}_i) of the equation is referring to the reconstructed representation of the hidden/compressed representation of the original input that was encoded by the encoder [7].The (W) is referring to the weight matrix of the decoder and the (b) is the bias value or vector for the decoder [7].

2.Denoising AutoEncoder

Denoising AutoEncoders are another type of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders that attempts to reconstruct the original input given from its "Noisiest" form by corrupting the original input through a corrupting function that that sets some inputs received to zero and the output that is the result of the calculation is more robust to noisy input data and can be highly useful for classification of data [4,8,9].The Noisy

representation is the sum of the original input and the “Noise” added to the representation through the corruption function applied on the original input [4,8] , as it is labeled in (figure 9) as received from [4]

$$z = x + y$$

Figure 9 : The Noisy representation produced equation

The (z) is the noisy representation of the input that is the sum of the original input (x) and the noise that has been added to the original input through the corruption function (y) [4].The problem that is the main concern of researchers when developing an Artificial Neural Network Denoising Autoencoder is the identification of the amount of features that are available from the original input , if there are too many features the model might overfit the input data and convergence of the system to reach a suitable output is going to become very slow when trying to reach an outcome, however if there are a small number of features for the input then the model might underfit the lack of relevant features [9].The overfitting of data happens when the training error for the model decreases however the validation (test) error increases.The main aim of the Denoising autoencoder is to learn important representation of the input data in order to recover the missing data when the data becomes corrupt and to successfully reconstruct the original input data from the it’s noisiest form [9].

The complete process of the denoising autoencoder is portrayed in figure (10) that is received from [4].

Figure 10 : The complete process of the Denoising AutoEncoder

(x) is the original input of the system in which the “Corrupted input” is generated by destroying or partially corrupting some of the inputs in the original input (x) by setting their original values to the value of (0) in order to generate the corrupted input (\hat{x}) expressed as $[\tilde{x} \sim qD(\tilde{x}|x)]$ [11]. The second step of the process is the “encoding” or “mapping” of the corrupted input (\hat{x}) generated from the first step to it’s hidden/compressed representation that is labeled as (y) and it’s equation is expressed as $[y = f\theta(\tilde{x})]$ in which the (fθ) is the function of the encoder in which it either uses the identity function for linear mapping or the sigmoid function for non-linear mapping [2,11].The third step is to reconstruct the original input from it’s hidden/compressed representation that is labeled as (y) and reconstructed in (z) and it’s equation is expressed as $[z = g\theta(y)]$ in which the (gθ) is the function of the decoder in which it either uses the identity function for linear mapping or the sigmoid function for non-linear mapping [2,11].The final and most important step of the denoising autoencoder process is the process of training the parameters for error reconstruction [11] , in which a variant of (Bernoulli Distribution) is used which is usually the Kullback-leibler (KL) probability distribution as seen in most literatures.The most important point is the encoding of the hidden/compressed representation of the original (x) and assigning it to (y) to allow (y) to gain and capture and extract much more important information on the original input (x) [11].The most important feature of Artificial Neural Network Denoising AutoEncoder is the process of extracting valuable information and hidden factors that are present in the input that are deemed invisible in the majority of cases if the encoding process is not applied to the original input this allows the denoising autoencoder to

extract hidden information about the original input that allows the model to learn and extract valuable features of the original input [11].

3.Convolutional AutoEncoder

Convolutional AutoEncoders are another type of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders in which the input and output layers are connected to filtering operators referred to as (convolutions) [12]. Those convolutions are in turn connected to the hidden/compression layer's functions such as the (sigmoid function) for non-linear mapping [2,12]. The data that is received from the different layers of the input and convolutions layers are directly connected and sent to the corresponding layers of the output and it's convolutions [12]. The Convolutional AutoEncoders have Three additional parts apart from the encoder and decoder that perform the filtration and mapping of the data which are (Convolution , Pooling , Deconvolution) [13]. The process of Convolutional AutoEncoders is depicted in (figure 11) as received from [13]

Figure 11 : The Process of Convolutional AutoEncoders

The input received is passed on to the convolutions which are the filtration processes of the data while encoding the data [13,14]. The convolution's output is typically the summation of the filtration process and the input with which it matches or overlaps in the filtration process [13]. Elements generated by each one of the filters is considered as one feature map in which each filter has one stride of their own which is a component in filters that acts as a constant value to regulate the output in which the summation of these feature maps are ultimately the output of the

convolutions which are then passed to the pooling phase [13]. The Pooling phase is a process that maps the generated feature maps in the encoder convolutions (filters) to the corresponding decoder convolutions [13,14]. In the Pooling process each input feature map is divided to regions based on the available regions in the pooling region and are of the same size as the corresponding output feature maps and are mapped to each other [14]. The Pooling has a filter of its own that is commonly referred to as the "Kernel" that has no specific values or indicators but the pooling process can benefit from two types of indicators which are the "Max" and "Maximal" that determine the type of the pooling operation [13]. After the pooling process has concluded the neurons in the pooling operations shall be reduced and hence reducing the complexity of the computations [14]. The process of converting the feature maps generated by the pooling process to an output is referred to as Deconvolution [14]. Deconvolution is the third part in which the same convolution process and filtration is applied on the feature map generated from the encoder's

convolution and pooling process with different or inverted parameters in order to make sure the output that is going to be generated has the same size as the input previously generated by the encoder's convolutions and pooling process [13]. The mathematical equation of the Convolutional AutoEncoders are portrayed in (figure 12) as received from [13]

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} r = \text{pool}(F(\text{conv}(X) + b_1)) \\ \hat{X} = G(\text{de_conv}(r) + b_2) \\ \text{minimize } L = l(X, \hat{X}) + \Omega \end{array} \right.$$

Figure 12 : The Mathematical equation of the Convolutional AutoEncoders

In the first part of the equation (r) is referring to learned features when the original input has gone through the filtration process (convolution) and has been passed to the pooling phase to be mapped to the corresponding feature map in the convolution of the decoder [13]. The (b1) and (b2) are the bias values that act as a constant to regulate the equation of the Convolutional AutoEncoder [13]. The (x) is the input from which the data has been gathered and is sent to the convolution and filtration process [13]. The (F) is referring to the non-linear activation function in which (Sigmoid Activation Function) is most commonly used however the non-linear activation function can house the (Hyperbolic tangent function) and the (Rectified linear function) [2,13,14]. In the first part of the equation (r) is assigned the calculation of the pooling process in which the filtration (convolution) of the input along with the bias value have been passed to the activation function (F) and have been sent to the Pooling phase after that and the output of the pooling phase and the previous calculations are assigned to (r) [13]. In the second part of the equation the (\hat{x}) is referring to the reconstruction of the input (x) that have been extracted from the pooling phase and sent to the activation function (G) [13]. The (G) is the Activation function of the decoder in which the most common activation function for non-linear mapping is the (Sigmoid Activation Function) [2,13]. The second part of the equation assigns the output of the activation function (G) that houses the calculation of the deconvolution process along with the second bias constant value (b2) to the (\hat{x}) [13]. In the third part of equation the (L) which is referring to reconstruction error is assigned the calculation of the regularization term (Ω) which can be seen as reconstruction loss function and the

most common reconstruction loss function (regularization term) to be used is the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence formula [10,13,14], which then the The regularization function is added with the (l) function that measures the differences between the original input (x) and the reconstructed input (\hat{x}) to train the model to learn [13]. Unsupervised learning methods such as the Convolution AutoEncoders can be stacked on top of each other to form much deeper and more complex hierarchies that can solve more complex problems by using greedy learning and fine-tuning the weights using back-propagation to form feature vectors for SVMs [15].

4. Contractive AutoEncoder

A contractive autoencoder is an unsupervised deep learning technique that helps a neural network encode unlabeled training data [21][22]. A contractive autoencoder makes this encoding less sensitive to small variations in its training dataset. This is accomplished by adding a regularizer, or penalty term, to whatever cost or objective function the algorithm is trying to minimize [21]. The end result is to reduce the learned representation's sensitivity towards the training input [21]. This regularizer needs to conform to the Frobenius norm of the Jacobian matrix for the encoder activation sequence, with respect to the input. This autoencoder will be activated only when other encoding schemes fail to label a data point.

5. Undercomplete Auto Encoder

Under complete Autoencoder is a type of Autoencoder where the most crucial data features are captured by an undercomplete autoencoder. Undercomplete autoencoders have a hidden layer dimension that is smaller than the input layer dimension. This makes it easier to extract significant features from the data. By penalizing the $g(f(x))$ for deviating from the input x, it reduces the loss function. It takes in an image and tries to predict the same image as output, thus reconstructing the image from the compressed bottleneck region so the target being the same as

the input. This form of compression in the data can be modeled as a form of dimensionality reduction.

The loss function used to train an undercomplete autoencoder is called reconstruction loss, as it is a check of how well the image has been reconstructed from the input[5], which can be seen in figure 6. Where the x represents the ground truth and the \hat{x} represents predicted output.

$$L = |x - \hat{x}|$$

Figure 13 : The reconstruction/norm loss equation

An autoencoder whose code dimension is less than the input dimension is called undercomplete and that's mainly because it captures the most salient features of the training data.

6. Variational Autoencoder

Variational AutoEncoders are another type of AutoEncoders that learn about a model through variational distribution, this gives variational autoencoders the ability to capture specific point variances in each specific data in a specific state [26]. Variational AutoEncoders generalizes linear models in order to allow for non-linear probabilistic explorations of the model [26]. Variational AutoEncoder uses the (latent variable) which is a variable that is used to generate values when the dependencies between the dimensions are high [27]. If (X) is a datapoint for every single data then we must ensure that the model generate a value that is similar to (X) in which the latent variables are used and the operation is expressed in (Figure 14) as received from [27].

$$P(X) = \int P(X|z; \theta)P(z)dz.$$

Figure 14 : Probability Density Function in Variational AutoEncoders

$P(X|z; \theta)$ in the equation allows to determine the dependence of (X) value on the (Z) value which is the latent variable by using the law of total

probability [27]. The result is outputted in the form of Gaussian distribution in which the model has a mean and a covariance that is equal to the identity matrix [27].

Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoder Application

1. AutoEncoders in Recommendation Systems

Recommender systems as a generic definition are systems that recommend certain products or services to customers and user that in which the system assumes this product or service will be of valuable use to the customer and user by predicting the utility (usefulness) of the certain item to the user and provides suggestions on the item[16]. Recommender Systems have always been able to provide personalized suggestions and recommendations on certain products to users however with the growing complexity of the products and the ever increasing amount of users and different sets of information of those users and products and hence a new solution is needed for the proposed problem [17]. In the previous literatures many researches have tried to incorporate the deep learning methods including the Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders for their high performance [17]. Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders have been seen as very efficient unsupervised learning models that perform really well for feature extraction and dimensionality reduction and reconstruction and extraction of various invisible and missing features from original inputs given to the model such as the case of denoising autoencoders and sparse autoencoders [7,11,17]. Incorporating Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders have had a very positive impact on the Recommendation systems in which the quality of the system increased by increasing the quality of the recommendations that are recommended to the Users [17]. Recommendation System generally deals with multiple categories of data ranging from different attributes of an item to the properties of a user's profile and the previous interactions between the user and the item in terms of user history such as the ratings of a user for a particular item [17,18,19,20]. The typical Recommendation

systems struggle with the common problems that occur in Recommender System such as the “cold-start” problem in which new items that are submitted to the system are recommended poorly due to limited amount of ratings by the users who have rated the certain item hence the limitation of the typical recommender system types requires a new solution that overcomes the traditional problems faced by those recommender systems[17 , 18 , 19].The incorporation of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders in the recommendation systems have proven to increase the performance due to its abilities to understand and learn non-linear relationships between the item that is being recommended and the users of the system [17].Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders overcome the data sparsity (scatteredness) problem that is faced by the traditional recommendation system by extracting meaningful information and features from a variety of sources and not relying only on one source base[17].Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders are emphasized for their precise accuracy in the recommendation of items to users as well as their “noise” handling and their information and feature extraction abilities from a variety of Heterogeneous sources of information [11,17,19].In the following section the different types of AutoEncoders that are used in the field of Recommendation system shall be discussed.

1.1 Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (CDAE)

As previously mentioned in the paper Denosing AutoEncoders are AutoEncoders that attempt to reconstruct a noisy form of the hidden representation of the input with the aim of extracting features and learning more about the features the input has through corrupting the original input data[4,8,9].However Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (CDAE) is a recommender system that relies on the use of AutoEncoder with the collaborative principle of the recommender system to make recommendations [17].The (CDAE) does not rely on the explicit ratings of the user when a user rates an item but rather depends on a partial feedback from the user in which the (CDAE) uses integer values for, an example of this would be when a user is interested in a movie and presses the like button on the movie the value

the (CDAE) assigns to the movie is (1) otherwise it will assign (0) [17].The (CDAE) is mainly focused on predicting ranking rather than the explicit rating a user gives to a certain item when interacting with an item [17].The structure of The Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (CDAE) is shown in (figure 15) as received from [17].

Figure 15 : The structure of CDAE

The first set of nodes are referring the preferences of each user in which each one of the user preference nodes are connected to the corresponding item that the user has preferred in which the user node is depicted in gray color in the first set of nodes[17].The weight matrix for the user is calculated by multiplying the preferences (W1) by the items to form (w) the weight matrix in which all of the mentioned part create the encoder part of the (CDAE)[17].The (W2) and the bias nodes form the decoder of the model [17].The reconstruction process of the corrupted input takes place using the Conditional Gaussian distribution as it is depicted in (figure 16) as received from [17]

$$h(\tilde{r}_{pref}^{(u)}) = f(W_2 \cdot g(W_1 \cdot \tilde{r}_{pref}^{(u)} + V_u + b_1) + b_2),$$

Figure 16 : The gaussian distribution for the reconstruction process of the corrupted input

In which the (Vu) is the weight matrix for the user preference by calculating the (W1) along with the items and both (b1) and (b2) are the bias values that regulate the equation.The f() and the g() are activation functions [17].

1.2 Autoencoder-based collaborative filtering (ACF)

Collaborative filtering is a type of recommender systems that recommends items to a user based on the ratings of multiple users for that item with the notion that users who are interested in a certain set of item should be recommended those set of similar items [18,19].The Collaborative Filtering collects ratings for that set of similar items from a set of users to analyze the utility and importance of the certain item to the current user who's being recommended the item[18,19].AutoEncoder-based Collaborative filtering (ACF) is an AutoEncoder that is used in recommender systems that is focused on users and not rating values explicitly [17].The (ACF) takes the ratings for the item and turns it into a vector of zeros (0) and ones (1) and takes that vector as the input data and not the rating itself [17].The input layer in AutoEncoder-based recommender systems has the ratings for specific items that the user has rated , The hidden layer computes the probability of a certain value to be given to a corresponding item in the output layer [17].The Structure of the AutoEncoder-based recommender system is shown in (figure 17) as received from [17].

Figure 17 : The structure of the AutoEncoder-based Collaborative Filtering

The rows on the left side (input layer) represent items in which each row is an item , each square in the item represents a rating value in which the values are in the range of [1,5] , The first item is given the rating value of (1) and the second item is given the rating value of (4) [17].The hidden layer calculates the probability of rating value of the items on the right (output layer) based on the items on the left (input layer) [17].The hidden layer uses $(r_q = \sum_{k=1}^k a^k_j)$ to predict the probability of the rating value for the corresponding items in the (output layer) based on the ratings of the (input layer) [17].one of the disadvantages of the AutoEncoder-based Collaborative Filtering (ACF) is it's noticeable struggle when dealing with values that are not integer values [17].Another disadvantage of the (ACF) is that even if multiple (ACF) were stacked together it will not have a remarkable impact on the performance of the model apart from a small increase in accuracy but it tremendously increase the computational complexity and overhead [17].(ACF)'s prediction decreases noticeably when the input data vectors are not complete and are missing ratings for the items leading to an increase in data sparsity (scatteredness) in which even the traditional Collaborative Filtering recommender system struggles in [17,18,19].

1.3 Collaborative filtering neural network (CFN)

Collaborative Filtering Neural Network (CFN) is another type of AutoEncoder recommender systems that is based on Stack Denoising AutoEncoder (SDAE) due to the robustness property of Denoising AutoEncoders , hence incorporating (SDAE) structure in (CFN) leads to more robustness when dealing with inputs [17].Collaborative Filtering Neural Network (CFN) unlike (ACF) directly takes the rating values the users have given to certain items as a vector for the input data and not converting them to other formats of input data[17].The (CFN) integrates other properties and attributes into the computation process in each layer such as user profile and preferences and the descriptions of the items in terms of the provided data on an

item from its name to the description to its categories [17].The encoding process in the Collaborative Filtering Neural Network corrupts the rating values that have been given to an item hence the corrupted rating becomes the main aspect of the reconstruction process that shall take place to reconstruct the corrupted original input [17].The structure of Collaborative Filtering Neural Network is shown in (figure 18) as received from [17]

Figure 18 : Structure of Collaborative Filtering Neural Network

The The first row of input nodes are the corrupted ratings that act as input to the Collaborative Filtering Neural Network (CFN) along with incorporated side information on the item and the user profiles such as user preferences and the item name and descriptions and extra information [17].The reconstruction process of the corrupted item ratings are expressed in (figure 19) as received from [17]

$$h(\{\tilde{r}^{(i)}, s_i\}) = f(W_2 \cdot \{g(W_1 \cdot \{\tilde{r}^{(i)}, s_i\} + \mu), s_i\} + b),$$

Figure 19 : Reconstruction Formula of the corrupted ratings

(Si) refers to the side information that has been provided such as the user profiles and the item descriptions whereas $\tilde{r}^{(i)}$ refers to the corrupted ratings that have been corrupted by the input corruption function in the encoding process [17].W1 is the weight matrix of the equation , μ is the basis vector that is used as a constant value to regulate the equation and (g) is referring to the activation function [17].Collaborative

Filtering Neural Network (CFN) adds much more accuracy in predictions and accelerates the training process and by passing the (SDAE) the model's robustness increase remarkably[17].

1.4 Supervised Neural Recommendation (SNR)

Supervised Neural Recommendation (SNR) is another form of Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders in which takes in the input from input source in order to extract the most important features and informations from the input and then attempts to reconstruct the input to make recommendations to the users and customers[17].Supervise Neural Recommendation (SNR) applies the concept of stacked AutoEncoders (SAE) in order to reconstruct the input and recommends a product or a service to the customers [17].The most important operations that the Supervised Neural Recommendation (SNR) does are (Feature extraction , reconstruction of input , classification) [17].The input of the (SNR) is the rating value vector for a specific item that contains the ratings for that item [17].The process of classification is classifying similar items in order to find the similarities between the items [17].Reconstruction of the inputs is very crucial and plays a very important role in the prediction of the rating between users who have rated the item and specific items alike [17].The structure of the Supervised Neural Recommendation is depicted in (figure 20) as

received from [17].

Figure 20 : The structure of the Supervised Neural Network

Input item (i) refers to the specific item that is being processed in which a vector with the rating values for the specific item (i) is shown that contains the ratings for the item in which the nodes with a black cross in their middle showcase verified ratings however the gray nodes refer to unverified or weak ratings [17]. The Classification process as mentioned previously in (SNR) classifies the items based on their similarities to each other and finds the similarities between them, in (figure 19) the gray nodes in the classification section refer to the results received by the classification process when classifying items based on their similarities which eventually leads to an improved process of feature extraction [17]. The final stage of the Supervised Neural Recommendation (SNR) is the reconstruction of the input in order to determine similarities between the users who have rated the item and the item [17]. The Supervised Neural Recommendation can be expressed as the following formula received from [17].

$$\begin{aligned} & \min F_R(r, W_e, W_r, b_e, b_r) \\ & + \alpha \sum F_c(r, W_e, W_c, b_e, b_x) \\ & + \frac{\beta}{2} (H(W_c) + H(W_r) + H(W_e)) \end{aligned}$$

(α) and (β) in the above equation are the regularization parameters that are used to adjust the weights in the process and (W_e) and (b_e) are

two parameters that are used in the process of extracting features from the inputs that have been received [17]. (W_r) and (b_r) are two parameters that are used in the reconstruction process of the Supervised Neural Networks (SNR) in which the similarities between the users rating for an item and the item itself is being processed [17]. (W_c) and (b_c) are referring to the parameters that are used in the classification process of the (SNR) [17]. (F_R) is referring to the cost function when the reconstruction process takes place to reconstruct the inputs [17]. (F_c) is the cost function for the classification process when the classification takes place [17]. The (H) is referring to the Huber function which is a regression loss function that acts as a medium solution between two or more loss functions by taking the outliers into consideration [17,23]. The Huber loss function is a function that is robust to the outliers and behaves quadratically when dealing with small residuals (difference between observed values and predicted values) however it behaves linearly with larger residuals [23].

1.5 Trust-aware collaborative denoising autoencoder (TDAE)

The Trust-Aware Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (TDAE) is a type of AutoEncoder based recommendation system that depends on the correlation between rating and trust data for its learning process by implementing two Denoising AutoEncoders (DAE)'s [17]. The (TDAE) model is implemented by connecting the user's preferences through two (DAE)'s by incorporating a weighted layer [17]. The weighted layer is used to regulate or balance the utility (usefulness) of the rating with the trust data [17]. The input of the Trust-Aware Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (TDAE) essentially is a corrupted version of the input that is corrupted by the input corruption function in the (DAE)'s That sets some of the inputs received to the value of (0) [4,8,11,17]. The structure of the (TDAE) is depicted in (figure 21) as received from [17].

Figure 21 : The structure of The Trust-Aware Collaborative Denoising AutoEncoder (TDAE)

The (\hat{R} and \hat{T}) are referring to corrupted input which are the ratings and the trust data that have been corrupted by the corruption function in the denoising autoencoders [4,8,11,17]. The (Z_u^R) and (Z_u^T) refers to the specific preferences that the user (u) has learned from the corrupted version of the ratings and the trust data which have been corrupted by the corruption function [4,8,11,17]. Due to the non-linear nature of the relationship between the ratings and the trust data and the difference in their distributions both (Z_u^R) and (Z_u^T) need to be merged together because they have higher variance hence a weighted hidden layer with the following equation have been proposed to merge both (Z_u^R) and (Z_u^T) together [17].

$$P_u = \alpha Z_u^R + (1 - \alpha) Z_u^T$$

The personal preferences of the user (u) is denoted by (P_u) in which (α) is a hype-parameter that regulates the effects made when combining and merging (Z_u^R) and (Z_u^T) [17].

2.AutoEncoders Applied To Classification Problems

2.1 Stacked Denoising AutoEncoders (SDAE) in Classification of Remote Sensor Images

The conventional methods for image classification have proven themselves to be insufficient in terms of their accuracy and hence a new method for image classification with the aid of artificial intelligence was needed more specifically a deep learning method [24]. Remote Image capturing in essence is the process of capturing a specific land or area and converting it into a sort of semantic representation which proved itself to be the focal point of urban planning and mapping [24]. Generally there are two main approaches to implement the remote sensing image classification which are reflected in (parametric) and (non-parametric) approaches in which the non-parametric approach is more popular to be used with artificial intelligence due to the fact that parametric approach requires the exact distribution of data from the beginning which may not always be present in artificial intelligence [24]. In [24] a Stacked Denoising AutoEncoder has been implemented to classify the remote images that are captured by delegating the noisy input to the multiple layers of the stacked denoising autoencoder in which the (greedy-layer) is used to train all the other layers, The backpropagation algorithm is then used to extract all the necessary characteristics and features from the input and then the algorithm optimizes the whole network by checking the errors [24]. A Denoising AutoEncoder is an AutoEncoder that corrupts the original input by adding “noise” to the input through the corruption function by corrupting the original input in which the output of decoder layer attempts to rebuild the original input and gaining valuable information from the corrupted input on the original input and have proven itself to be very efficient when used in classifications [4,8,9]. A Stacked Denoising AutoEncoder on the other hand are multiple layers of Denoising AutoEncoder that have been stacked on top of each other and noise is added through all the layers of the encoder in which the whole model follows unsupervised learning but with an extra supervised learning layer which is the backpropagation algorithm

[24]. Backpropagation neural network in essence is a network that follows the (feedforward) method and is trained by applying the error backpropagation algorithm to train the network [24]. Backpropagation is used for supervised classification of the features that have been extracted by the denoising autoencoders from the original input that have been labeled in which a specific feature vector will be associated with the corresponding label of data that the backpropagation algorithm can work on to classify the labels [24]. The backpropagation algorithm has two main operations which are the (forward propagation) and (error backpropagation) in which the input vector is passed forward in the propagation and the predicted category is received in the output layer in which the actual corresponding category is compared with the predicted category to determine the classification that has been produced in order to determine the accuracy of the accurate prediction [24]. The parameters and weights of the network are then modified and adjusted based on the error backpropagation that checks the errors of each layer [24]. The Semantic representation of the remote images captured shall be assigned to a pixel and the correlation (strength of relationship) between the current pixel and the neighboring pixel are calculated in terms of their shape and texture in the form of a $(S \times S)$ square image block [24]. The information that are present in each pixel such as the texture, Spectrum and Space can be extracted using the Stacked Denoising AutoEncoder (SDAE) [24]. The label of each block of images is expressed in the form of a vector whose dimensions are the number of categories for that pixel [24]. Each Node in the classification result vector can only take binary values either (0) or (1) because each node in the vector is a category if the pixel belongs to one type of category that category will be given the value of (1) and the rest of the nodes will be set to the value of (0) and shows that the pixel have been classified to that specific category [24]. The general structure of the (SDAE) application in the remote sensing image classification is depicted in (figure 22) that has been received from [24]. In (figure 22) a portion or a specific area is assigned to a (3×3) image block or a matrix in which the colors in the matrix are (4-band) gray values that are fed to the (SDAE) in order to extract the necessary features

of the area or land in terms of the texture, shape and space [24].

Figure 22 : (SDAE) Application in The Remote Sensing Image Classification

The (SDAE) then Labels the pixel based on the category that the pixel belongs to in which the label is in the form of a vector that contains many categories each category is expressed as a node that takes the value of (1) or (0) in which the node or category that the pixel belongs to shall be given the value of (1) and the rest of the categories will be set to (0) [24]. Two main formulas are used in order to determine the accuracy of the classification and compare the results with the actual results in real life and on the ground which are (Overall Accuracy) formula and (Kappa Coefficient) in which both of the formulas work on the (confusion matrix) that is generated to determine the accuracy of the classifications [24]. The Confusion Matrix is depicted in (Figure 23) as received from [24].

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} & \dots & m_{1n} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} & \dots & m_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ m_{n1} & m_{n2} & \dots & m_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 23 : The Confusion Matrix

The (Overall Accuracy) formula is a formula that calculates the classification error by calculating (m_{ij}) which is the number of pixels for the actual object (i) that has been put in the place of the test object (j) as can be seen in (Figure 24) received from [24]. The (n) is the total number of categories that one specific pixel may belong to when classifying the pixel to determine which category the pixel belongs to [24].

$$OA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n m_{ii}}{\sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{i=1}^n m_{ij}}$$

Figure 24 : Overall Accuracy Formula

The (m_{ii}) is the number of pixels belonging to object (i) that have been accurately classified [24]. The Overall Accuracy formula struggles when a category has too much elements and is affected by the diagonal elements in the confusion matrix hence the (Kappa Coefficient) formula is the most suitable selection when choosing a fairly improved formula to determine the classification errors in which all the elements in the confusion matrix are utilized and calculated and the classification results and the actual results on the ground are compared [24]. The Kappa Coefficient formula is depicted in (Figure 25) as received from [24].

$$K = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^n m_{ij} - \sum_{i=1}^n m_{i+} m_{+i}}{N^2 - \sum_{i=1}^n m_{i+} m_{+i}}$$

Figure 25 : The Kappa Coefficient

In the above formula the (N) is referring to the total number of pixels, The (n) is referring to the total number of categories, The (m_{i+}) and (m_{+i}) are referring to the sum of the elements in the i th row in (m_{i+}) and the sum of the i th column in (m_{+i}) of the confusion matrix [24]. In Stacked Denoising AutoEncoders the number of hidden layers and the neurons matters to learn more features in (SDAE) the more the number of neurons in each hidden layer the better the system can be trained to learn more features [24].

2.2 Deep Convolutional AutoEncoder for Radar-based Human Activity Classification

Radar-based Human Recognition have been applied in multiple domains and is of great importance due to the direct impact on human lives which can be reflected in the application of

pedestrian recognition in vehicles for the safety of the pedestrians and notification of the driver for nearby pedestrians and multiple security applications and domains [25]. Convolutional AutoEncoders which are a type of AutoEncoders that take the input given and pass them through the different filtration layers (convolutions) and processes them using the activation function then maps them to the corresponding decoder filtration layers to get the proper output, has been seen as a much better solution than the typical Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and the ordinary AutoEncoder for handling the classification problem in correspondence to the Radar-Based Human Activity Classification [25]. Modern Radars use the micro-Doppler analysis method to classify and distinguish movement in a certain environments which paved way for smaller and more portable devices that can be used indoors [25]. The Convolutional Techniques that are applied when dealing with micro-Doppler analysis are applied in the form of two operations the first is to extract the pre-defined features and characteristics of the input which may be in the form of bandwidths and envelopes, computationally transformed features or discrete cosine coefficients, Second operations is the feature selection and dimensionality reduction of the input in which a fixed set of features shall be fed to a classifier to process the specific set of test data which can be a Support Vector Machine (SVM) [25]. Micro-Doppler analysis uses (Spectrograms) which are merely a representation of the (time to frequency) distribution of the measured Micro-Doppler signature [25]. Spectrograms are expressed as the modulus of the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) which is depicted in (Figure 26) as received from [25].

$$STFT(m, \omega) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x[n]w[n-m]e^{-j\omega n}$$

Figure 26 : Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) Formula

In the above formula the $x[n]$ refers to the input signal that has been received, The $w[m]$ refers to the window function which is in essence a

function that regulates the above formula in order to prevent any spectrogram leakages and acts as a regulator for the formula [25]. Physical features are extracted by measuring the properties of the spectrogram or the Cadence Velocity Diagram (CVD) that is related to the actual human movement parameters that is expressed as the Fourier transformation of each frequency bin in the spectrogram as depicted in (Figure 27) as received from [25].

$$\Delta(v, \omega) = \left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} STFT(n, \omega) e^{\frac{-j2\pi n v}{N}} \right|$$

Figure 27 : Fourier Transformation formula

Writer's Acknowledgements

I would like to Thank God for giving me the power and patience to complete this research paper and has made my path easy for me, I would like to Thank my Lecturers at (Qaiwan International University - Universiti Malaysia Franchise) for inspiring me to explore beyond my boundaries and the limits that has been set by community and academic standards, I would like to Thank the Author's efforts of those Authors whose research papers I have used as sources for my research on Artificial Neural Network AutoEncoders, I would also like to Thank my classmate "Hala AbdulHakim" for her contributions in (Undercomplete AutoEncoder) and (Contractive AutoEncoder). I hope this research paper benefits the readers and act as basis for more extensive research and work on the topics of Artificial Intelligence and Artificial Neural Networks. Thank you Very Much.

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